

Beauty Vlogger Marketing: A Systematic Literature Review and Future Research Agenda

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ABSTRACT

Influencer marketing is thriving as a result of the rising level of technological advancement and global increase in internet users. The component of influencer marketing known as "beauty vlogging" focuses specifically on harnessing the influence of beauty vloggers as a powerful promotional instrument for selling cosmetic items throughout the world. Even though considerable research has been done in this area, a thorough understanding of the phenomenon is still lacking. This review consolidates the current status of research embracing this practice. We utilize 81 research publications that discuss the influence of beauty vloggers and their impact on consumer behaviour. Through a meticulous investigation, an integrative framework has been created employing antecedents, mediators, moderators, and probable consequences on consumer behaviour. Three categories; theory, context, and methodology have been created to group the unexplored future research directions. Discussion is also centred on the theoretical and practical ramifications of marketing by beauty vloggers...

Keywords *Beauty vlogger marketing, blogger marketing, influencer marketing, social media marketing, social media, cosmetic industry, systematic literature review*

INTRODUCTION:

It is in the nature of humans to appear lovely and presentable. As a result, they wear makeup as a means of self-expression, independence, and confidence. Makeup has become popular and in-vogue recently, especially among metropolitan residents who have a penchant for keeping up with the current trends (Ananda & Wandebori, 2016). Employees working in the corporate sector, the entertainment industry, and other such areas that appreciate a professional's presentability usually apply makeup and other cosmetic items. Nowadays, men also prefer wearing cosmetics on special occasions, in addition to women. Men working in the film industry are required to apply makeup every day (Sanny et al., 2020). Earlier, celebrity endorsement has historically been the most successful marketing strategy used by a variety of cosmetic firms to define their own personalities, develop positive attitudes toward their products, and build brand equity (Choi & Rifon, 2012). Here the celebrity endorser has been defined as, "an Individual who enjoys favorable public recognition, which he/she uses on behalf of consumer good by appearing with it in an advertising. The celebrity endorser is very well known to the general public. He/she can be an athlete, sports person, an actor, or in general an entertainment figure who possess wide public recognition for at least the target audience for the

brand" (Schimmelpfennig, 2018; Mccracken, 1989). Companies pay large sums of money to these celebrity endorsers to promote their brand product. However, with increasing advancement in technology, one of the most powerful tools of promotion in this digital era is the internet. With the COVID-19 outbreak, which saw an increase in people using social media for leisure and virtual social interactions, social media influencer marketing grew more quickly (Kim & Kim, 2021). Marketers have begun to look at social media influencers as the next brand ambassadors because they seem to exhibit traits shared by peers and superstars. These celebrity-peer hybrids serve as active brand ambassadors, but they also give customers the benefit of social belongingness, meeting their needs for consistency, identity, connection, and attachment. More and more companies are now collaborating with social media influencers to connect with their target market, market their products, and inform consumers about how to use them (Tafheem et al, 2022).

The internet allows users to express themselves on various social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and various other platforms where everyone is free to express themselves without any barrier (Abdullah et al., 2020). Moreover, there has been positive growth in the number of internet users all over the world. As per the Global Digital Report 2018, there are 5.135 billion mobile

phone users and 3.196 billion social media users worldwide, and these numbers are rising annually by 4% and 13% respectively (Kaur & Kumar, 2020). Despite the fact that many individuals use social media sites like YouTube and Instagram for interaction and amusement, there has recently been a strong push toward marketing, particularly influencer marketing in the cosmetics industry (Lopez & Islam, 2021). A recent trend in social media culture is the "presentation of the self", which encompasses putting oneself on screen in front of others along with self-branding methods (García-Rapp, 2017). It may be claimed that the internet and social media phenomena have a significant influence on customer preferences and purchasing intents, having an impact that is comparable to that of word-of-mouth. In other terms, social media might be seen as a new kind of word-of-mouth or E-WOM (electronic Word of Mouth) (Sutanto & Aprianingsih, 2016). Here, social media influencers can be defined as, "independent third-party endorsers who have developed sizeable social networks by sharing details about their personal lives, experiences, and opinions publicly through texts, pictures, videos, hashtags, location check-ins, etc" (Ki & Kim, 2019; Freberg et al., 2021). Social media influencers have established a sizable following on social media, with these users crediting SMIs as reliable opinion leaders who originate from "people like me." Due to the private information they choose to disclose about the intimate elements of their life on their social media pages, these micro-celebrities are more personable, approachable, and real than the traditional celebrities (Tafheem et al., 2022).

The 2006-launched video-sharing website YouTube frequently witnesses the same scenario. Ever since its original introduction in 2006, YouTube has gained positive feedback from its users throughout the globe. With the help of YouTube, social connections and a more equitable relationship between media stars and users has now become possible as the website has expanded considerably over the past few decades (Lee & Watkins, 2016; García-Rapp, 2017; Kim & Kang, 2018; Sánchez-Fernández & Jiménez-Castillo, 2021; Lee & Lee, 2021). Among the various sectors prevalent on YouTube, the presence of the beauty industry has markedly expanded. Millennials watch YouTube videos of beauty influencers to learn about products and develop their makeup skills. The young consumers frequently assume that they may obtain trustworthy and genuine information from these amusement platforms as social media incorporates users' personal networks and offers user-generated material (Gupta et al., 2017; Chen & Dermawan, 2020; Lee & Lee, 2021). Beauty vloggers, or beauty influencers, are a new breed of social media professionals who make videos or other social media posts on cosmetics and beauty products. The majority of the cosmetics industry see this as a chance to introduce their brand to a new consumer base. Thus, cosmetic companies offer beauty vloggers a partnership to promote their product on their YouTube channel and other social media accounts such as Instagram, Facebook page, Snapchat, etc (Afifah, 2019).

Not only is it beneficial for cosmetic brands, but reciprocally it enables beauty vloggers in gaining

popularity and fame from this collaboration, thus establishing a mutually rewarding symbiotic relationship. With the growth of digitalization, consumers now like to watch reviews of a product before spending their hard-earned money, which results in increased brand awareness and perceived quality for cosmetic brands, which highly influences purchase intention by the target audience (Hermenda et al., 2019). Many beauty vloggers give free products to their subscribers for increasing the rating and subscribers on their channel. These giveaway products are also viewed as another promotional strategy adopted by cosmetic brands to capture a large market segment. Those beauty vloggers who have higher subscribers on their YouTube channel charge money for featuring brands' products on their channel. It is known as Paid Promotions (Tran & Nguyen, 2020). The hype of internet and social media usage has accelerated the pace of the establishment of beauty vloggers and their community on YouTube. Featuring the product on the YouTube channel, Facebook page, and Instagram account can be contemplated as the most feasible promotional tool adopted by various cosmetic brands (Elseidi & El-Baz, 2016).

1.1 Motivation of the study

The following reasons in particular have inspired the current comprehensive review of studies on beauty vlogger marketing. First, despite the fact that earlier research has shown a variety of attributes of beauty vloggers (e.g. trustworthiness, credibility, attractiveness, and expertise), attributes of audience (e.g. user-influencer personality congruence, influencer, influencer-brand fit, self-concept, match-up concept), and interactional elements between beauty vlogger and their target audience (e.g. parasocial interactions, informational value, meaning transfer, and emotional bond) and its various consequences on consumers (e.g. purchase intention, recommendation, acceptance of product, brand image, and brand attitude) still the rapidly expanding body of research on the phenomena of beauty vloggers or beauty influencers has not been subjected to a systematic evaluation or comprehensive analysis. Therefore, we continue to lack intellectual and academic understanding of how marketers might benefit from this new instrument called beauty vlogging marketing. Second, the body of beauty vlogger literature is fast growing and pertinent additions are coming from numerous study domains. As a result, there is currently a very fragmented corpus of knowledge that requires organization to develop. To get the best results from beauty vlogger marketing, marketers need to understand the effects of different attributes of vloggers on consumers' perception and form integrative mental models that synthesize all the relevant information from multiple disciplines. Third, beauty vlogging is a significant domain among academics because it is being recognized as a crucial social media concept that will influence social media marketing in the future. Therefore, it is timely and significant to conduct a systematic assessment of high-quality research findings from articles that have been published in renowned academic peer-reviewed journals and different sources.

This systematic review makes several advancements to marketing theory and practice. First, we provide a

summary of pertinent research and map the major themes that have been looked at so far by scholars. Second, we offer a comprehensive analysis of the body of prior research on the subject. Third, we integrate and expand a variety of conceptual frameworks and research findings to elucidate the beauty vlogging phenomenon and its effects on consumer behaviour outcomes. The conceptual framework can serve as a theoretical foundation for future researchers to build a clear understanding of influencing phenomenon before forming any marketing strategies. Fourth, we provide a promising agenda for future study by identifying a number of research needs.

The following is the outline of this article. An explanation of our review process is presented first, followed by a descriptive and thematic summary, followed subsequently by a categorization of the findings. The results of previous research are combined into an integrated framework of the phenomena influencing beauty vlogger marketing. Finally, we discuss the implications of this study for future research and practice and provide suggestions for future research directions.

2. METHODOLOGY

For the objectives of this study, which include providing academics and practitioners with an integrative framework of the existing knowledge, offering a high-quality synthesis and organization of the SMI literature, identifying research gaps and opportunities for future research, a systematic literature review approach is deemed to be most appropriate. The guidelines established by Paul and Criado in 2020 served as the foundation for this literature evaluation (Paul & Criado, 2020).

2.1 Data Selection

For a structured, systematic literature review, we have used three relevant databases: Web of Science, EBSCOhost research databases, and Scopus. These three databases are chosen as they provide the most relevant literature. Also, these databases have ample literature available on marketing and consumer behaviour, which is quite relevant for our study.

The papers that are used in this systematic review paper are in line with the other systematic literature reviews in the fields of marketing and consumer behaviour published in high-impact factor journals. We have limited our research to peer-reviewed journal articles along with a few international conference articles available in the English language, excluding book chapters, non-referred proceedings, and editorials. Peer-reviewed articles are considered a valid source of information and hence can increase the quality of our study. To increase the articles

under review, we have used a few good quality international conference articles to understand variables better. To expand the scope of our study, both empirical and theoretical articles are used.

Plethora of literature is available on celebrity endorsement and social media influencing marketing narratives, that too in different fields, but limited attempt was made to synthesis this literature in a systematic way. Initially, we searched for broader keywords like beauty influencing or social media influencing that are directly related to our topic. After getting the results, we scanned the keywords or the choice of phrases used by different researchers in title and abstract to get to the core of our study. Different keywords used by various authors were found, noted down, and included in every new search for fine tuning to produce the final one. The keywords are used pertinently, and hence disclosing the pattern. Using the Boolean OR and AND operators, keywords searched were: “beauty influencer” OR “beauty vlogger” OR “beauty blogger” OR “digital influencing” OR “social media influencing” AND “beauty” OR “YouTube marketing” AND “Beauty” OR “YouTube marketing” AND “Fashion” in all the three databases used. Although the keywords are not comprehensive, but we are confident that it has gathered the significant studies.

We have searched the above-mentioned keywords in title, keywords, and abstract as used in different systematic review in the month of April 2026. The initial search articles were 326 in Web of Science, 112 in Scopus database, and 88 in EBSCOhost research database, making a total of 526 articles. After eliminating the articles that were not available in English (34), we were left with 492 articles. Next the duplicate articles (177) were removed, leaving 315 articles. 28 articles were intractable, hence eliminated. The title and abstract of the leftover articles were manually read and eliminated all the irrelevant articles (104) leaving us with 183 journal articles. For the remaining articles we conducted a full-text screening. (10) more articles were excluded as we were unable to extract these articles leaving us with 173 journal articles. After reviewing the full-text of the articles, (104) more articles were eliminated as these were out of our study’s scope leaving us with 79 journal articles. Next, we reviewed the referencing list of the articles selected, also known as backward screening, 2 additional studies were including making it a total of 81 relevant sample journal articles for our systematic review literature (shown in Figure 1).

FIGURE 1: Search strategy

2.2 Data Coding

After getting the final sample of journal articles, the next step is to read the full-text of the articles select to fetch all the relevant information for the purpose of recording and summarizing from the selected articles. For eliminating the human error and representing the results in the most transparent way, a data extraction form was used. Each article was coded according to (1) year of publication, (2) journal title, (3) authors, (4) methodology used (qualitative, quantitative, mixed method approach), (5) type of article (empirical, theoretical, and review), (6) research field (marketing, management, or any other), (7) social media platform used, (8) countries, (9) key findings, (10) future research agenda, (11) implications, and (12) limitations. This coding categorization helped us in extracting the relevant articles from different databases.

3. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

This section of the paper is one of the most important sections as it explains the basic description of the studies included in our systematic review. This portion varies in different systematic review papers according to the theme and choice of topic. In this segment of the paper, observations have been made based on contextual and technical characteristics of the papers included in our study like year of publication, methods applied, article type, publication outlets, research field, countries under study, and the social media platforms used by different authors. These characteristics are important to study as it helps in getting the thorough subject knowledge and help us to identify gaps in the literature to make our study more attractive and effective.

3.1 Year of Publication

Since, the research in this field is at its initial stage of investigation, it is no surprise that the oldest paper we got related to our study was in 2015. Various studies have

been published over the span of 10 years from 2015-2026 (as shown in figure 2). Although the pace of study creation is slow, still it is contributing significantly in the existing body of knowledge. Moreover, during the COVID 19 period, lockdown situation has started a culture of work of home giving a boost to the influencing culture. In 2015 and 2016, only 1 relevant article was published in each year. In particular, 4 articles were published in 2017 and

in 2018, it has increased to 5 articles. During 2019, 8 articles were published and it has peaked to 13 articles in 2020 which shows a notable growth in the marketing field. However, the number dropped to 10 in 2021 and 7 in 2022. Moreover, 8 articles in 2023, 6 articles in 2024, 12 articles in 2025 and 4 articles in 2026 were also considered. The data for this particular year (2026) have only covered the studies published till March 2026.

Figure 2 No. of Articles per year

3.2 Paper Type and Method used

Out of the 81 journal articles included in our systematic review, the largest portion is covered by the empirical studies (67%; n=54) which largely relied on quantitative data. On the other hand, the qualitative studies (33%;

n=27) are lesser in number when compared with empirical studies (as illustrated in figure 3). This shows that a lot of improvement have been made in the literature over a period of time in terms of development of conceptual framework, theoretical background, and more in depth understanding of the beauty vlogging phenomenon in the marketing field. Many researchers have taken theoretical studies as a base and made a conceptual model using the variables retrieved from qualitative studies.

Figure 3 Articles per year

3.3 Research Field and Publication Outlets

Most of the articles study the impact of beauty vlogger's influence on consumers purchase intention which is studied under consumer behaviour, so most of the journal articles belong to marketing field (n=24). Beauty influencers share the content related to various product recommendation and on different social media platforms so these are mostly covered by marketing field. The second up in the line is information and general management field (n=10) as different attributes of consumer's behaviours are studied under the theories of management. Followed by media (n=3), interdisciplinary (n=3), gender studies (n=2), and humanities and social sciences (n=1), cultural, economic, and social sustainability of human beings (n=1). The variety of fields under study depicts the interdisciplinary nature of

beauty vlogger influencing. Table 1 shows the variety of related journals used by researchers to publish their manuscript. The highest number of articles used in our systematic review are published in Psychology and Marketing (n=7), Journal of Business Research (n=6), Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services (n=6), followed by sustainability (n=3), International Journal of Consumer Studies (n=3) and International Journal of Advertising (n=2). Other articles are published in Journal of Product and Brand Management, Fashion and Textiles, Celebrity Studies, and various others. Since the content related to our systemic review is very scant and limited so we also included various international conference proceedings in our study (Journal articles = 79; conference proceedings = 3).

TABLE 1 List of journals included in our study

Research Field	Journal	No. of Articles
Marketing	Psychology and Marketing	7
General Management, Ethics, Gender and Social responsibility	Journal of Business Research	6
Marketing	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	6
Cultural, Economic, and Social Sustainability of Human Beings	Sustainability	3
Marketing	International Journal of Consumer Studies	3
Advertising	International Journal of Advertising	2
Marketing	Journal of Product and Brand Management	2
Marketing	Humanities and Social Sciences Communications	2
Marketing	Fashion and Textiles	1
Marketing	Marketing Intelligence and Planning	1
Marketing	Journal of Marketing Management	1
General Management and Humanities	Sage Open	1
Celebrity Marketing	Celebrity Studies	1
Media and Communication studies	Convergence: The international Journal of Research into New media Technology	1
Management Operations	The TQM Journal	1
Language and Linguistics	Journal of Pragmatics	1
Media and Communication Studies	Media, culture and Society	1
Interdisciplinary	PLOS ONE	1
Management	California Management Review	1
Marketing	Journal of Promotion Management	1
Gender Studies	Journal of Gender Studies	1
Logistics	International Journal of supply chain management	1
General Management	Journal of Applied Business	1
Information Management	Online Information Review	1
Humanities and Social Sciences	Pertanika Journal of Social and Humanities	1
Media Studies	Multimedia Tools and Application	1

General Management	International Journal of Organization Analysis	1
Marketing and General Management	Journal of Management and Marketing Review	1
Interdisciplinary	Journal of Risk and financial Management	1
Big Data and Social Science Networks	International Journal of Data and Network Science	1
Interdisciplinary	Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review	1

3.4 Citation Analysis

For increasing the effectiveness of our systematic review, citation analysis is done using Google Scholar. The citation for each article obtained from the systematic review process were extracted from Google Scholar. The top 15 highest cited research articles accounts for 89% out of the total 44 articles extracted. The highest cited articles are: Lee & Watkins (2016), Schouter et al. (2020), Sokolova & Kefi (2019), Berryman & Kavka (2017), Hou (2018), Garg & Bakshi (2024), Haehlein et al (2020), Ladhari et al. (2020), Torres et al., (2019), Wiedmann & Mettenheim (2020), Konstanatopoulou (2018), García-Rapp (2017), Kim & Kang (2018), Gupta et al. (2017), Balabanis and Chatzopoulou (2019), and Choi & Lee (2019). 11 articles were cited less than 10 times were not included in the table 2. The citations done in interdisciplinary journals increases the effectiveness of our systematic review.

TABLE 2 Citation counts as on 28 August 2022

Authors	Citation Count	Journal
Lee and Watkins (2016)	764	Journal of Business Research
Schouter et al. (2020)	672	International Journal of Advertising
Sokolova and Kefi (2019)	661	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Studies
Berryman and Kavka (2017)	201	Journal of Gender Studies
Hou (2018)	196	Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies
Garg and Bakshi (2024)a	165	Humanities and Social Sciences Communications
Haehlein et al (2020)	162	California Management Review
Ladhari et al. (2020)	155	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services
Torres et al (2019)	129	Psychology and Marketing
Wiedmann and Mettenheim (2020)	109	Journal of Product and brand Management
Konstanatopoulou (2018)	82	International Journal of Organizational Analysis
García-Rapp (2017)	79	Celebrity Studies
Kim and Kang (2018)	71	Journal of Business Research
Gupta et al. (2017)	60	Multimedia Tools and Applications
Balabanis and Chatzopoulou (2019)	59	Psychology and Marketing
Choi and Lee (2019)	55	Fashion and Textiles
Delbaere (2020)	53	Psychology and Marketing
Feng et al (2020)	48	International Journal of Advertising
Kim and Kim (2021)	47	Journal of Business Research
Wang et al (2015)	47	Online Information Review
Britt et al. (2020)	40	Journal of Interactive Advertising
Dekavalla (2019)	32	Media, Culture and Society
Sánchez-Fernández and Jiménez-Castillo (2021)	23	Journal of Marketing Management

Garg and Bakshi (2024)b	23	Humanities and Social Sciences Communications
Hassan et al (2021)	16	PLOS ONE
Kaur and Kumar (2020)	14	The TQM Journal
Lee and Lee (2021)	12	International Journal of Consumer Studies
Djafarova and Maston (2021)	12	International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising
Putri and Abdinagoro (2018)	11	International Journal of Supply Chain Management
Nosita and Lestari (2019)	11	Journal of Management and Marketing Review
Rosara and Luthfia (2020)	10	Journal of Distribution Science

3.5 Social Media Platform studied

Majority of the researchers have taken YouTube (45.09%; n=24) as their main social media platform for conducting their study on beauty vloggers. It is not an eye-opener, as YouTube is a video content sharing platform (as illustrated in figure 4). Also, the number of beauty vloggers has increased tremendously in the past couple of years owing to lockdown situation. Not only the beauty vloggers, but the number of subscribers and viewers have also increased considerably. Second most studied platform is Instagram (13.72%; n=7). This platform also allows beauty vloggers to make short reels (videos) of about 30 sec or above. Vloggers generally use this

platform for showing quick review of products. The third most used social media platform is Blogs (9.80%; n=5). Researchers have taken blogs under consideration for qualitative studies using content analysis. Moreover, for giving a more generic and efficient view to the study, many scholars have taken multiple platforms (17.64%; n=9) like Facebook, Snapchat, Twitter, Tik Tok, and others. Various studies (9.80%; n= 5) have taken universal perspective and does not disclose the social media platform they have used. Though YouTube is the most used social media platform in the existing literature, future research should also examine the effectiveness of using other social media platform like Instagram (as it allows content creators to grab more audience from Generation Z and baby boomers).

FIGURE 4 Social media platforms studied

3.6 Countries studied

The data extracted for our systematic review study reveals that majority of the authors have not disclosed (34.56%; n=28) the country they had studied. It is mostly prominent in qualitative and theoretical research articles. Considering the empirical studies, Indonesia (9.87%;

n=8) is the most studied country by researchers as it is having a huge cosmetic market which is expected to growth even higher in the coming period. The next up in the line is India (8.64%; n=7), United States (7.40%; n=6), followed by Korea (3.70%; n=3), UK (3.70; n=3) Vietnam (2.46%; n=2), Portugal (2.46%; n=2), and various others (as shown in figure 5). Some researchers have also considered taking samples from multiple countries

(2.46%; n=2) for increasing the effectiveness of their research articles.

Figure 5: Studied Populations by empirical studies

4. THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Thematic analysis is used for synthesising the data obtained from these manuscripts into broader themes. In doing so, all the key variables and constructs, purpose, key arguments, hypothesis, methodology, research gaps of each journal article were analysed in depth to get the better knowledge about the framework of beauty vlogger influencing and marketing. At first, the descriptive information of all the 81 selected research articles was outlined and initial thematic names were given. The articles having the same variables and constructs either using same construct name or different construct name are

segregated into similar themes. Then the full text of each article in different themes was analysed and compared. After this, all the segregated themes were revised to remove the chance of any human error and we finally came up with three broad themes. These themes are (1) Source Characteristics and its consequences on Consumer Behaviour, (2) Audience Characteristics and its consequences on Consumer Behaviour, and (3) Interactional Elements and its consequences on Consumer Behaviour.

Table 3 contains the list of articles that fall under each theme. Various articles contain constructs that can be classified under multiple themes and hence many articles are appearing in all the three themes.

TABLE 3 Research themes in the reviewed articles:

RESEARCH THEMES	REFERENCES
Source Characteristics and its consequences	Ramadanty et al. (2020); Handriana et al. (2019); Choi and Lee (2019); Delbarere (2020); Balabanis and Chatzopoulou (2019); Torres et al. (2019); Konstantopoulou et al. (2018); Wiedmann and Mettenheim (2020); Hassan et al. (2021); Tran and Nguyen (2020); Ladhari et al. (2020); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Kim and Kim (2021); Kim and Kang (2018); Gupta et al. (2017); Rosara and Luthfia (2020); Schouter et al. (2020); Nugraha and Agus (2020); Costa et al. (2021); Hou (2018); Dekavalla (2019); Haenlein et al. (2020); Bhatia (2020); Zhang (2018); Carissa et al. (2021); Lee and Watkins (2016); Manchanda et al. (2021); Djafarova and Matson (2021); Pereira et al. (2023); Filieri et al. (2023); Ashraf et al. (2023); Venciute et al. (2023); Mabkhot et al. (2022); Sesar et al. (2022); Hmoud et al. (2022); Kanwar and Huang (2022); Wong and Wei (2023); (Arendt, Till, Gutsch, & Niederkrotenthaler, 2025) (Garg & Bakshi, 2024);
Audience Characteristics and its consequences	Feng et al. (2020); García-Rapp (2017); Wang et al. (2015); Nosita and Lestari (2019); Delbarere (2020); Torres et al. (2019); Kim and Kim (2021); Kim and Kang (2018); Schouter et al. (2020); Hou (2018); Carissa et al. (2021); Tafheem (2022); Lee and Watkins (2016); Venciute et al. (2023); Koay et al. (2023); Ren

	et al. (2023); Wong and Wei (2023); Pei et al., (2026); (Maulidy, Zaini, & Sanjani, 2025); (Liu, Costa, Yasin, & Ruan, 2025); (Putri & Setiawan, 2025); (Keasey, Lambrinoudakis, Mascia, & Zhang, 2025); (Fauzi, et al., 2024); (Abdulla & Saberi, 2026); (Kumar, et al., 2024); (Koay & Lim, 2025)
Interactional Elements and its consequences	Lopez and Islam (2021); Handriana et al. (2019); Britt et al. (2020); Putri and Abdinagoro (2018); Kaur and Kumar (2020); Choi and Lee (2019); Delbarere (2020); Ladhari et al. (2020); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Kim and Kang (2018); Lee and Lee (2021); Berryman and Kavka (2017); Rosara and Luthfia (2020); Nugraha and Agus (2020); Castillo-Abdul et al. (2021); Lee (2019); Zhang (2018); Carissa et al. (2021); Tafheem et al. (2022); Lee and Watkins (2016); Sánchez-Fernández and Jiménez-Castillo (2021); Manchanda et al. (2021); Simanjuntak et al. (2017) Evers & Daalmans (2022); Ashraf et al. (2023); Mabkhot et al., (2022); Zhang and Choi (2022); Koay et al. (2023); Bailey et al. (2023); Hmoud et al. (2022); Ren et al. (2023); Kanwar and Huang (2022); Wong and Wei (2023); (Borchers, 2025); (Harst & Angelopoulos, 2024); (Cheah, Koay, & Lim, 2024)

4.1 Source Characteristics and its Consequences on Consumer Behaviour

The first and the most crucial theme in this systematic review is the ‘source characteristics’ of beauty vloggers. Plethora of literature is available on the source characteristics models, but Ohanion source credibility model and source attractiveness model are the two of the most widely used models in endorsement marketing. A major proportion of available literature has examined source characteristics from celebrities’ point of view. But now with the increasing use of technology in our daily life, consumers have shifted towards influencers. Using the source credibility model, researchers have revealed that it has three main dimensions namely, trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness and also considered its impact on purchase intention using emotional bond and attitude towards the product as the mediator.

However, other scholars have also studied the influence of different attributes like homophily, authority, and approachability of the source on the information seeker. Another study conducted by (Wiedmann & Mettenheim, 2020; Garg & Bakshi, 2024a) illustrates the impact of trustworthiness, attractiveness, and expertise of influencers towards the purchase intention and price premium using the intervening role of brand satisfaction, brand image, and brand trust. However, only few authors have conducted a comparative analysis between celebrity endorsement and endorsement by influencers.

Other studies have examined the role of knowledge, reliability, helpfulness, confidence, and articulation in forming trust which leads to cosmetic purchases. Tran and Nguyen (2020) have studied parameters such as credibility (brand-related communication), authenticity, effectiveness, deception and trust in vlogger and their effect on purchase intention (Ndasi & Cheung, 2026). Sokolova and Kefi (2019) have studied the intervening role of para-social interaction between source credibility model and purchase intention. Apart from source credibility, source attractiveness is another major component studied by researchers. Physical

attractiveness, social attractiveness, familiarity, and similarity also influences purchase intention.

4.2 Audience Characteristics and its consequences on Consumer Behaviour

The second theme in this systematic review is the audience characteristics. In order to know about the effect of beauty vlogger influencing, it is important to understand the perceptions and perspectives of consumers. Lee and Watkins (2016) examined the effect of brand-user imaginary fit by comparing pre and post behaviour of consumers. They revealed that after watching the vlogs, there is significant difference in the customers’ perception regarding the luxury brands. While it is acknowledged that a multitude of factors affect how consumers perceive companies, the results of this study suggest that relationships between audiences and vloggers, serving as brand ambassadors, can benefit luxury businesses. Studies such as Tafheem et al. (2022) also highlight the role of influencers in marketing operations, which may be seen as "a form of marketing in which marketers select and finance SMIs to construct and endorse their brand image in the minds of the influencer and the followers of these influencers." This study asserts that users frequently search for both real and ideal self-congruities in a variety of circumstances, subsequently concluding that users relate to SMIs more strongly when they present a true image of themselves, such as by going makeup-free or discussing skin problems, leading to actual self-congruity. Given that self-congruity can be connected to personality-based images and that the beauty industry falls under the umbrella of hedonic consumption, self-congruity is a psychological notion that can be applied to the sector. It is also affirmed that beauty influencers are more enticing than conventional superstars because of their sincerity and innovative personalities.

Schouten et al. (2020) compared the effectiveness of wishful identification in celebrities and influencers. It is primarily the level of connection with another person that one feels they share, or the desire (wish) to resemble them. They revealed that influencers are seen as more relatable and approachable than conventional celebrities, similar to having a distant companion. Influencers frequently

address their followers directly in their posts, conveying a sense of intimacy that helps followers view them as peers. The opportunity to contact with influencers, and comment and react on their posts facilitates such identification. Moreover, consumers are more likely to believe product claims made by endorsers that they can identify with. Delbaere et al. (2020) and (Sporl-Wang, Krause, & Henkel, 2025) also illustrated that if there is congruency between the personality of beauty vlogger and that of the consumer, it will result in effective brand engagement which ultimately leads to high purchase intention.

Another empirical study was conducted by (Torres et al., 2019) which shows the effect of congruency between the beauty influencer and a brand towards consumer attitude. They illustrated that understanding how effective an endorsement is depends on how well-matched the endorser and the product are. Positive customer responses to advertising are more likely to be produced when a celebrity (in our study beauty vloggers) and brand fit well together than when they don't. The empirical findings indicate that opinions toward the endorsement are more strongly influenced by the brand's congruence with the digital influencer who is endorsing it. The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by (Kim & Kim, 2021) in which they have discussed about the importance of multi-layered relationship including brand-consumer relationship, influencer-consumer relationship, and influencer-brand relationship. Additionally, they have mentioned that influencers specifically use the trust and relationships they have already built with their followers to spread the brand's message. Utilizing relational trust, the foundation of an influencer-follower relationship, is crucial. Carissa et al. (2021) illustrated that consumers perceive congruence when an influencer endorses particular products in line with their areas of expertise. Influencers with whom the consumers identify in terms of personality, way of life, or taste are more likely to be followed by them. Customers' sentiments towards influencers will change and purchase intention will increase if there is a higher degree of congruence between them and the consumers.

4.3 Interactional Elements and its consequences on Consumer Behaviour

The third and the last theme in this systematic review is the interactional elements. Understanding the interactional features as a marketing technique is essential for fully comprehending the phenomenon of beauty vlogging. Lopez and Islam (2021) studied the engagement rates of both micro and macro influencers on Instagram, arguably the most user-friendly social media platform. They found that macro influencers had a higher rate of engagement than micro influencers. Additionally, in order to increase the engagement rate of their respective audiences, both micro and macro influencers employ more entertaining content than relational and useful field information. The significance of parasocial interactions between beauty vloggers and viewers has been highlighted by various scholars (Lee and Watkins, 2016; Choi & Lee, 2019; Lee & Lee, 2021; Garg & Bakshi, 2024b). Parasocial interaction is the one-sided connection

between a beauty vlogger and their audience. The like, dislike, share, and comment buttons in each video enable a one-sided (parasocial interaction relationship) contact between the beauty vlogger and their viewers. Researchers have discussed the readiness to give information more in terms of the parasocial interactions between vloggers and viewers. Additionally, these encounters lead to a better match between brand and user imagery, which raises buying intent (Handriana et al., 2019; Manchanda et al., 2021; Sokolova and Kefi, 2019). The importance of parasocial contact in encouraging consumer purchase intention via content diagnosticity, vicarious expression, and perceived risk has also been covered by other researchers (Lee and Lee, 2021). Here, content diagnosticity is the method of problem-solving made available for online product evaluation. Indirect virtual encounters that increase customer familiarity with the product are known as vicarious expression. In today's internet world, YouTube video reviews are recognized as reliable sources of information before making any purchases and for assessing the post-purchase experience. This investigation demonstrated how viewers' vicarious experiences of content diagnosticity and vicarious expressiveness, which lowers risk perceptions and raises purchase intentions, are encouraged by parasocial interactions. The significance of parasocial interactions in the YouTube community or environment is shown by this research.

The role of parasocial interactions in shaping views about luxury goods and raising purchase intention for premium products was also covered by (Lee and Watkins, 2016). To gauge customers' impressions of luxury brands, researchers employed brand luxury, luxury brand value, and brand-user imagery fit. Here, brand luxury represents how customers see symbolic status. The total evaluation of how well they mesh with the brand's customers is known as the brand-user-imagery fit. The appraisal of a luxury brand's entire worth is known as brand value. According to the findings, customers' pre and post-luxury brand impressions vary more when they engage with vloggers often, which raises their likelihood of making a purchase.

Along with parasocial interactions, emotional bonding and informational value are further interactional factors that affect followers' behaviour toward companies that influencers promote. The findings of (Sánchez-Fernández and Jiménez-Castillo, 2021) research shows that when vloggers form an emotional link with their intended audience and when the influencer's message is viewed as having high quality or strength, followers are more likely to foresee positive word-of-mouth towards the recommended products and be more likely to make purchases. The findings of this study are consistent with the research conducted by (Nugraha and Agus, 2020), in which they highlighted how aspects of homophily such as attitude, value, look, and background of vloggers, create an emotional bond with their viewers that affects purchase intention. They also spoke about how the vlogger's fame had no discernible influence on their decision to buy.

5. Framework Development

The integrative framework in Figure 6 sheds light on the phenomena of vlogging and vlogging marketing on multiple social media platforms and is generated from a synthesis of the results of this systematic research. This thematic analysis highlights the topic's interdisciplinary character. Therefore, supplemental tables are supplied for additional in-depth information relevant to dynamics in relationships and interactions in an effort to make the framework as obvious and simple as feasible. Keep in mind that the tables do not provide comprehensive listings. Instead, they highlight key aspects.

The antecedents and consequences employed by researchers in earlier work have been taken into account in the development of this integrated framework. The topics used for the systematic review contain three

categories for antecedents: (a) source characteristics; (b) audience characteristics; and (c) interactional components. Consumer attitudes (such as purchase intent, readiness to share information, and the efficacy of advertising) and behavioural consequences (such as loyalty to influencers) at different levels make up the majority of the common effects that researchers look at (see table 4). Effects of mediators (see table 5) and moderators (see table 6) are also employed to create this complete framework. An integrated framework that shows the efficiency of beauty vlogger influence and marketing has been created by combining all the components. Future academics may utilize this dynamic paradigm, to get deeper understanding of the phenomenon of beauty vlogging.

FIGURE 6 Interactive framework from the thematic analysis

TABLE 4 Key antecedents and consequences of beauty vlogger marketing

	Antecedents	Consequences	Effect	Citations
Source Characteristics	Argument quality	PI	+	Ramadanty et al., (2020);
	Source credibility	PI, Attitude toward the beauty influencer, PSI, EWOM intention, brand awareness	+	Ramadanty et al., (2020); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Nosita and Lestari (2019); Carissa et al., (2021); Manchanda et al., (2021); Mabkhot et al., (2022); Sesar et al., (2022)
	Source attractiveness	PI, willingness to share information, PSI, Brand satisfaction, brand image, brand trust, premium price, Attitude toward the endorsement, brand attitude, influencer defense	+	Ramadanty et al., (2020); Handriana et al., (2019); Lee and Watkins (2016); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Wiedmann and Mettenheim (2020); Torres et al., (2019); Pereira et al., (2023); Filieri et al., (2023); Ashraf et al., (2023); Wong and Wei (2023)
	Source perception	PI	+	Ramadanty et al., (2020);
	Trustworthiness	Brand satisfaction, brand image, brand trust, PI, Premium price, attitude towards product/brand, content sharing intention, brand attitude, PSI, purchase behaviour, credibility	+	Wiedmann and Mettenheim (2020); Choi and Lee (2019); Pereira et al., (2023); Filieri et al., (2023); Ashraf et al., (2023); Venciute et al., (2023); Mabkhot et al., (2022); Hmoud et al., (2022)
	Physical attractiveness	willingness to share information, PI, PSI, Trust, credibility, attitude towards product/brand, content sharing intention, purchase behaviour, influencer defense	+	Handriana et al., (2019); Lee and Watkins (2016); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Choi and Lee (2019); Pereira et al., (2023); Ashraf et al., (2023); Venciute et al., (2023); Hmoud et al., (2022); Wong and Wei (2023)
	Expertise	Willingness to share information, PI, Trust, brand satisfaction, brand image. Brand trust, premium price, attitude towards product/brand, content sharing intention, Attitude toward the beauty influencer, brand attitude, PSI, purchase behaviour, credibility	+	Handriana et al., (2019); Nugraha and Agus (2020); Kim and Kim (2021); Ladhari et al. (2020); Wiedmann and Mettenheim (2020); Choi and Lee (2019); Carissa et al., (2021); Pereira et al., (2023); Filieri et al., (2023); Ashraf et al., (2023); Venciute et al., (2023); Mabkhot et al., (2022); Hmoud et al., (2022)
	Attitude homophily	willingness to share information, PI, PSI, Trust, credibility, influencer defense	+	Handriana et al., (2019); Lee and Watkins (2016); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Pereira et al., (2023); Wong and Wei (2023)
	Value	Emotional Attachment	+	Nugraha and Agus (2020); Ladhari et al., (2020)
	Background	Emotional attachment	+	Nugraha and Agus (2020); Ladhari et al., (2020);
	Endorser type	Advertising effectiveness	+	Schouter et al., (2020);
	Social power	PSI	+	Kim and kang (2018);
	Authenticity	Trust, PI	+	Kim and Kim (2021); Tran and Nguyen (2020);
	Trust in the blogger	PI	+	Tran and Nguyen (2020)

	Vlogger Popularity	PSI, EWOM intention	+	Manchanda et al., (2021)
	Brand Attitude	PI	+	Filieri et al., (2023)
Audience Characteristics	Actual self-congruity	Informational influence, influencer defense, PI	+	Wang et al., (2015); Wong and Wei (2023)
	Ideal self-congruity	Informational influence	+	Wang et al., (2015);
	Functional Congruity	Informational influence	+	Wang et al., (2015);
	Product-Endorser fit	Advertising effectiveness	+	Schouter et al., (2020);
	Social Capital	PI	+	Kim and Kang (2018)
	Brand congruence	Attitude towards the endorsement, brand attitude, PI, engagement	+	Torres et al., (2019); Ren et al., (2023)
	Self-congruity	PSI, COBRA	+	Tafheem et al., (2022)
	Perceived congruence	Attitude toward the beauty influencer, PI	+	Carissa et al., (2021)
	Influencer intimate self-disclosure	PSI, PI	+	Koay et al., (2023)
Interactional Elements	Emotional attachment	WOM communication, PI for recommended brands, Intention to follow the influencer, intention to recommend the influencer, Susceptibility to SMI influence, SMI compliance intention, PSI	+	Sánchez-Fernández and Jiménez-Castillo (2021); Nugraha and Agus (2020); Zhang and Choi (2022); Bailey et al., (2023)
	Perceived information value	WOM communication, PI for recommended brands, PSI, credibility, brand image	+	Sánchez-Fernández and Jiménez-Castillo (2021); Ashraf et al., (2023); Mabkhot et al., (2022); Kanwar and Huang (2022)
	Vlogger's popularity	PI	-	Nugraha and Agus (2020)
	Beauty blogger involvement	PI	-	Putri and Abdinagoro (2018);
	Parasocial Interaction	PI, luxury brand perception, COBRA, EWOM intention, Susceptibility to SMI influence, SMI compliance intention, Perceived value, brand image, influencer defense	+	Lee and Lee (2021); Lee and Watkins (2016); Sokolova and Kefi (2019); Tafheem et al., (2022); Manchanda et al., (2021); Kim and Kang (2018); Bailey et al., (2023); Kanwar and Huang (2022); Wong and Wei (2023)
	Trust	Loyal to influencers, PI, Attitude toward the beauty influencer	+	Kim and Kim (2021); Hassan et al., (2021); Carissa et al., (2021)
	Entertainment Value	Credibility, PI	+	Mabkhot et al., (2022)
	Information Quality	Intention to follow the influencer, intention to recommend the influencer, attitude toward brand	+	Zhang and Choi (2022); Hmoud et al., (2022)
	Meaning Transfer	Attitude toward brand	+	Hmoud et al., (2022)

TABLE 5 Key mediators in the Beauty vlogging

Antecedents	Mediator	Consequences	Relationship	Citation
Argument quality; source attractiveness; source perception	Information acceptance EWOM	Purchase intention	The positive effect of argument quality, source attractiveness, and source perception toward purchase intention is successively mediated by information acceptance EWOM	Ramadanty et al., (2020)
Source Credibility	Information acceptance EWOM	Purchase intention	The is no significant impact of source credibility on purchase intention is successively mediated by information acceptance EWOM	Ramadanty et al., (2020)
Actual self-congruity; Ideal self-congruity	Blogger reader relationship quality; functional congruity	Informational influence	The positive effect of actual self-congruity and ideal self-congruity towards information influence is successively mediated by blogger reader relationship quality and functional congruity	Wang et al., (2015)
Source attractiveness; physical attractiveness; attitude homophily; expertise	PSI	Willingness to share information; brand-user imagery fit	The positive effect of source attractiveness, physical attractiveness, attitude homophily, and expertise towards willingness to share information and brand-user imagery fit is successively mediated by parasocial interaction	Handriana et al., (2019)
PSI	Brand-user imagery fit	Purchase intention	The positive effect of PSI toward purchase intention is successively mediated by brand-user imagery fit	Handriana et al., (2019)
Emotional attachment; perceived information value	Perceived influence	Positive WOM communication; Intention to purchase recommended brands	The positive impact of emotional attachment and perceived information value towards positive WOM communication and intention to purchase recommended brands is successively mediated by perceived influence	Sánchez-Fernández and Jiménez-Castillo (2021)
Endorser type	Identification; Credibility	Advertising effectiveness	The positive impact of endorser type towards advertising effectiveness (Ad attitude; Product attitude; Purchase intention) is successively mediated by identification (wishful identification; perceived similarity) and credibility (trustworthiness; expertise)	Schouter et al., (2020)
PSI	Luxury brand perception	Purchase intention	The positive effect of parasocial interaction towards purchase intention is successively mediated by luxury brand perceptions (luxury brand value; brand-user imagery fit; brand luxury)	Lee and Watkins (2016)
Dimensions of Homophily	Emotional attachment	Purchase intention	The positive effect of dimensions of homophily (i.e., attitude; value; appearance) towards purchase intention is	Nugraha and Agus (2020)

			successively mediated by emotional attachment	
Dimensions of Homophily	Vlogger's popularity	Purchase intention	The negative effect of dimensions of homophily (i.e., attitude; background; value; appearance) on purchase intention is successively mediated by vlogger's popularity	Nugraha and Agus (2020)
Parasocial interaction	Content diagnosticity; Vicarious expression; perceived risk	Purchase intention	The positive effect of parasocial interaction on purchase intention is successively mediated by content diagnosticity, vicarious expression, and perceived risk	Lee and Lee (2021)
Social power	PSI; social capital	Purchase intention	The positive impact of social power (i.e., expert; referent; legitimate; reward) on purchase intention is successively mediated by parasocial interaction and social capital (i.e., bonding; bridging)	Kim and Kang (2018)
Source credibility	Trust	Loyalty to influencers; Product attitude; purchase intention	The positive effect of source credibility (i.e., expertise; authenticity) on loyalty to influencers, product attitude, and purchase intention is successively mediated by trust	Kim and Kim (2021)
Source attractiveness	Trust	Loyalty to influencers; Product attitude; purchase intention	The positive effect of source attractiveness (i.e., homophily) on loyalty to influencers, product attitude, and purchase intention is successively mediated by trust. However, trust does not significantly mediate the impact of physical attractiveness towards the relative outcomes	Kim and Kim (2021)
Physical attractiveness; attitude homophily	Credibility; PSI	Purchase intention	The positive effect of physical attractiveness and attitude homophily on purchase intention is successively mediated by credibility and PSI. However, parasocial interaction does not significantly mediate the impact physical attractiveness towards purchase intention	Sokolova and Kefi (2019)
Social attractiveness	PSI	Purchase intention	The positive effect of social attractiveness towards purchase intention is sequentially mediated by parasocial interaction	Sokolova and Kefi (2019)
Dimension of homophily	Emotional attachment	Vlogger popularity	Emotional bond positively mediates the impact of two dimensions of homophily (i.e., attitude; value) on purchase intention. However, emotional bond does not significantly mediate the impact of another two dimensions of homophily (i.e., background; appearance) towards purchase intention	Ladhari et al., (2020)

Dimension of homophily	Vlogger popularity	Purchase intention	Vlogger popularity positively mediates the impact of three dimensions of homophily (i.e., attitude; value; appearance). However, vlogger popularity does not significantly mediate the impact of one dimension of homophily (i.e., background) towards purchase intention	Ladhari et al., (2020)
Expertise	Vlogger popularity	Purchase intention	The negative impact of expertise on purchase intention is sequentially mediated by vlogger's popularity	Ladhari et al., (2020)
Credibility traits of social media influencers	Trust	Cosmetic product purchase	The positive impact of credibility traits of SMI's (i.e., knowledge; reliability; helpfulness; confidence; articulation) on purchase of cosmetic product is sequentially mediated by Trust	Hassan et al. (2021)
Attractiveness; Expertise; Trustworthiness	Brand satisfaction; brand image; brand trust	Purchase Intention; Premium Price	The positive impact of attractiveness, expertise, and trustworthiness on Purchase intention and premium pricing is sequentially mediated by brand satisfaction, brand image, and brand trust	Weidmann and Mettenheim (2020)
Attractiveness; Brand congruence	Attitude toward the endorsement; brand attitude	Purchase intention	The positive impact of attractiveness and brand congruence on purchase intention is sequentially mediated by attitude toward the endorsement and brand attitude	Torres et al., (2019)
Vlogger's attributes	Attitude towards product; content sharing intention	Purchase intention	The positive impact of vlogger's attributes (i.e., attractiveness; expertise; trustworthiness) on purchase intention is sequentially mediated by attitude towards product and content sharing intention	Choi and Lee (2019)
Perceived credibility; Trust; Perceived behavioral control; subjective norms; perceived expertise; perceived congruence	Attitude toward the beauty influencer; brand attitude	Purchase intention	The positive impact of Perceived credibility, Trust, perceived behavioural control, subjective norms, perceived expertise, and perceived congruence on purchase intention is sequentially mediated by attitude toward the beauty influencer and brand attitude	Carissa et al., (2021)
Credibility; Vlogger popularity	PSI	EWOM intention	The positive impact of credibility and vlogger popularity on EWOM intention is successively mediated by parasocial interaction	Manchanda et al., (2021)
Attractiveness; Credibility; Trustworthiness	Attitude toward brand	Purchase Intention	Attitude toward brand mediates the relationship between dimension of credibility and purchase intention	Filieri et al., (2023)
Attractiveness; Credibility; Trustworthiness;	PSI	Purchase Intention	PSI mediates the effect of source credibility and fairness on purchase intention	Ashraf et al., (2023)

Similarity; Distributive; Information; Procedural; Interpersonal				
Credibility; Trustworthiness; Likability; Information Quality; Entertainment Value	Credibility	Purchase Intention	Credibility mediates the relationship between different social media characteristics and purchase intention	Mabkhot et al., (2022)
Influencer intimate self-disclosure	PSI	Purchase Intention	There is no significant impact of PSI in mediating the relationship between influencer intimate self-disclosure and purchase intention	Koay et al., (2023)
Influencer credibility	Brand awareness	Purchase Intention	Brand awareness played a significant mediated role between influencer credibility and purchase intention	Sesar et al., (2022)
Social media attachment	PSI	SMI compliance intention; Susceptibility to SMI influence	There is no significant impact of PSI in mediating social media attachment and SMI compliance intention. However, it mediated the relationship between social media attachment and susceptibility to SMI influence	Bailey et al., (2023)
PSI	Susceptibility to SMI influence	SMI compliance intention	Susceptibility to SMI influence positively mediates the relationship between PSI and SMI compliance intention	Bailey et al., (2023)
Social media attachment	Susceptibility to SMI influence	SMI compliance intention	Susceptibility to SMI influence positively mediates the relationship between social media attachment and SMI compliance intention	Bailey et al., (2023)
Social media influencer	PSI; Perceived value; brand image	Purchase intention	PSI, perceived value, and brand image sequentially mediates the relationship between social media influencer and purchase intention	Kanwar and Huang (2022)
Social attractiveness; physical attractiveness; attitude homophily; actual self-congruity; PSI	Influencer defense	Purchase Intention	Influencer defense fully mediates the relationship between physical attractiveness and purchase intention, and partially mediated the effect of attitude homophily actual self-congruity, and PSI on purchase intention. No mediation effect is seen between social attractiveness and purchase intention.	Wong and Wei (2023)

TABLE 6 Key moderators in the beauty vlogging

Antecedents	Moderator	Consequences	Relationship	Citation
Blogger reader relationship quality	Perceived interactivity	Informational influence	Perceived interactivity strengthens the relationship between blogger reader relationship quality and informational influence	Wang et al. (2015)
Functional Congruity	Perceived interactivity	Informational influence	Perceived interactivity has a negative effect on informational influence when there is low level of functional congruity	Wang et al. (2015)
Attributes of vloggers	Parasocial interaction	Luxury brand perception	Parasocial interaction strengthens the relationship between luxury brand perceptions (i.e., luxury brand value; brand-user imagery fit; brand luxury) and attributes of vloggers (i.e., social attractiveness; physical attractiveness; attitude homophily)	Lee and Watkins (2016)
Authenticity	Relationship strength	Trust	Relationship strength acts as a moderator such that higher authenticity towards vloggers result in higher amount of trust	Kim and Kim (2021)
Trust	Relationship strength	Loyalty to influencers	Relationship strength acts as a moderator such that trust in vlogger positively influences loyalty to the influencer.	Kim and Kim (2021)
Vlogger's attributes	Emotional bond	Attitude towards product	Emotional bond has a strong impact of vloggers attributes (i.e., attractiveness; expertise; trustworthiness) in framing attitude towards product	Choi and Lee (2019)
Vlogger's attributes	Emotional bond	Content sharing intention	Emotional bond between vloggers and audiences will affect vlogger's attributes on content sharing intention.	Choi and Lee (2019)
Self-congruity	Platform type	Parasocial relationship	The connection between self-congruity and parasocial relationships is not substantially moderated by platform type.	Tafheem at al., (2022)
Self-congruity	Platform type	COBRA	The relationship between self-congruity and COBRA is not substantially moderated by platform type.	Tafheem et al., (2022)
Expertise; Trustworthiness; Attractiveness; Content usefulness	Influencer-follower congruence	Purchase behaviour	Influencer-follower congruence moderates the effect of expertise and content usefulness on purchase intention. However, attractiveness and trustworthiness have no significant impact on purchase behaviour when moderated by congruence.	Venciute et al., (2023)
Influencer intimate self-disclosure	Congruence between consumer and influencer	PSI	The relationship between influencer intimate self-disclosure and PSI is not moderated by congruence between consumer and influencer	Koay et al. (2023)
PSI	Congruence between consumer and influencer	Purchase Intention	The relationship between PSI and purchase intention is substantially moderated by congruence between consumer and influencer	Koay et al. (2023)
PSI	Congruency between influencer	Purchase Intention	The relationship between PSI and Purchase intention is neither moderated by congruency between	Koay et al. (2023)

	and product; congruency between consumer and product		influencer and product nor by congruency between consumer and product.	
Advertising Disclosure	Influencer Type	Influencer credibility	There is no significant impact of influence type in moderating the effect of advertising disclosure on influencer's credibility.	Sesar et al., (2022)
Influencer Type	Brand stereotype (warmth and competence)	Online sales	There is no significance difference of influencer type on online sales when endorsing warm and competent brands	Ren et al., (2023)
Influencer characteristics (social attractiveness; physical attractiveness; attitude homophily)	Previous purchase experience	Influencer defense; purchase intention	There is no significant impact of social attractiveness and physical attractiveness on influencer defense and purchase intention when moderated by previous purchase experience. However, previous purchase experience negatively moderates the effect of attitude homophily on influencer defense and purchase intention.	Wong and Wei (2023)

6. Future Research Agenda

While our systematic research provides significant new information on a variety of social media influencer marketing-related topics, our knowledge of the myriad characteristics of vloggers (in terms of conversational styles, particular methods chosen for interaction, nature of para-social interactions etc.) is rather limited. Future research can seek to focus on the appropriateness of various types of vloggers for distinct contexts and for accomplishing different objectives. Vlogger marketing promotion on various social media platforms is a highly dynamic phenomenon that requires continual observation. Therefore, further studies on potentially significant connections are required to comprehend this complicated phenomenon and to broaden the notion. The future research agenda is divided into three primary sections: theory, context, and methodology, each of which includes a list of important concerns.

6.1 Theory

6.1.1 Theoretical extension

We learned from this comprehensive analysis of the existing studies that beauty vlogging marketing has garnered a lot of interest in recent times. Vlogging marketing has been connected by several scholars to a number of theories, including the theory of planned behaviour, the social comparison theory, the social exchange theory, parasocial interaction theory, the source credibility theory, the social attractiveness theory, and the persuasion theory (Putri & Abidinagoro, 2018; Sánchez-Fernández & Jiménez-Castillo (2021); Lee & Lee, 2021; Kim & Kim, 2021; Sokolova and Kefi, 2019; Weidmann & Mettenheim, 2020; Manchanda et al., 2021). To get a thorough understanding of the notion, several writers have

also utilised a variety of theories (Kim & Kim, 2021; Manchanda et al., 2021). Many researches, however, lack a sound theoretical foundation. The theories that are most often used include the persuasion theory, source attractiveness theory, source credibility theory, and social comparison theory. These studies are briefly discussed.

Researchers have applied social comparison theory to know the effect of parasocial interactions in creating luxury brand perception among the viewer's mind (e.g., Lee & Watkins, 2016). Persuasion theory has been used to determine how the communicator's processing skills impact whether the strength of the argument or other ancillary signals would influence the viewers' and customers' behavioural outcomes (Sokolova & Kefi, 2019). Researchers assess the efficacy of the message articulated by the vlogger using the source credibility model. The message conveyed by the vloggers will be seen by the audience as a more reliable source of information if they believe the source to be trustworthy and expert in their field (Manchanda et al., 2021). The source attractiveness model explains how a communicator's physical and social appeal affects the degree of attention and engagement they get from viewers. In this case, social attractiveness relates to the familiarity, likability, and likeness between the vlogger and their specific audience, whilst physical beauty refers to the vlogger's entire body. Customers are more susceptible to the impact of socially and physically appealing people (Kim & Kim, 2021). The signalling theory, social exchange theory, psychology-parasocial theory, megaphone effect, and two-way communication theory are some of the ideas that are seldom employed by researchers in their investigations. Future academics may utilize these ideas to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the concept. The beauty aesthetic notion may be made interdisciplinary by researchers working on cross-fertilization of theories from several fields.

6.1.2 Antecedents and Consequences

Prior research exploring the characteristics of beauty vloggers and the efficiency of beauty vlogging marketing mostly focused on credibility, trustworthiness, attractiveness, attitude homophily, expertise, self-congruity, and product-endorser fit. Future studies may employ a variety of different factors, such as value, approachability, inspirational, background, social power, trust, user-influencer personality congruence, and meaning transfer, that may have a significant effect on persuasion results. The phenomenon of meaning transfer is often employed in celebrity endorsements. Future studies may examine the effects of meaning transfer from the standpoint of beauty vloggers (Rosara and Luthfia, 2020). Frequently studied consequences in earlier literature were brand trust, brand attitude, and purchase intention as well as recommendations of approved brands and goods and EWOM (electronic word of mouth) intentions (Lee and Watkins, 2016; Sokolova and Kefi, 2019; Torres et al., 2019; Handriana et al., 2019; Ramadanty et al., 2020). Future research might explore attitudes towards beauty influencers, willingness to share knowledge, effectiveness of the influencers' promotional efforts, and perception of luxury brands (in particular) with special reference to influencers' promotional endeavours.

6.1.3 Mediators and Moderators

We may get deeper insights into phenomena by researching mediating and moderating effects. We therefore urge future studies to pursue this line of inquiry further and look at other factors that might mediate or otherwise impact the relationship between influencer marketing strategies and desired outcomes like engagement, buy intention, and sales. Parasocial interaction, emotional attachment, credibility, YouTuber popularity, brand satisfaction, brand image, brand trust, brand attitude, and trust are the most important mediators that have been employed in the previous researches. Loyalty to the influencer may be investigated further as a possible mediating component in the examination of the impacts of sponsorship disclosures. In order to examine the effect of beauty vlogging on purchase intention, it is important to include possible mediating elements in addition to customer loyalty, such as perceived congruency, brand-user imagery fit, and perceived influence. Considering moderators, the most important moderators in the previously published material, according to several authors, are parasocial interactions and emotional attachment/bond (Lee and Watkins, 2016; Choi and Lee, 2019). Relationship strength and perceived interactivity are other important moderators in addition to these two (Wang et al., 2015; Kim and Kim, 2021). When analysing customer reactions to vloggers' recommendations, future studies should take into account trust, consumer attitude, relationship quality, and perceived risk as the moderator. Additionally, in earlier research, the emphasis was placed more on mediating constructs and less on moderators. Therefore, moderators may be included in future studies to assess the magnitude of affiliation between viewers and beauty vloggers.

6.1.4 Message Strategies

A majority of the previously published material was geared toward advertising brands that micro celebrities or social media influencers utilize. It is advisable for future studies to delve further into the sponsorship issue and how it affects consumer purchase intent when promoted by beauty vloggers. Additionally, all researches have shown the beneficial effects of beauty vloggers' support. There are, however, very few researches that investigate the negative effects of product endorsements and how they affect customer purchasing decisions. We believe that future studies will benefit from looking at the dark side of influencer product endorsements.

6.2 Context

6.2.1 Product Focus

Since the term 'beauty vloggers' instinctively implies the usage of cosmetics, the bulk of preliminary research in the domain has exclusively looked at cosmetics. However, these beauty vloggers are expanding the niche areas in their videos and online content, creating broad, generalized content about different products and sectors. Today, many apparel firms work with vloggers to advertise their goods on various social media platforms. Jewellery and footwear industries, as well as clothing companies are looking at using vlogging as a powerful marketing tool. In order to make their videos seem more attractive, YouTube vloggers employ a variety of eye-catching home décor goods. As a result, furniture and home décor firms are contacting beauty vloggers to promote their brand products. Consequently, the product selection expands, indicating the potential of such campaigns across numerous industries. The effect of vloggers on cosmetic businesses has been studied in the past, but relatively few researches have been undertaken that provide comparisons between various goods and sectors that beauty vlogging has come to encompass directly or indirectly. It is advisable for future scholars to delve further into cross-product, cross-disciplinary comparisons. The majority of researches have looked at how domestic companies' purchase intentions of consumers are impacted by beauty vloggers. Only a few studies, however, have concentrated on marketing a global or foreign brand. Future studies should also investigate how sponsorship disclosure affects customer purchasing intentions.

6.2.2 Geographical reach

The two most popular social media platforms employed by different academicians in their studies are YouTube and Instagram. As per statistics from Statista.com, India has the largest YouTube and Instagram audiences (467 million users and 230.25 million users respectively) of all countries. Still, we found very few studies based on Indian respondents (e.g., Gupta et al., 2017; Bhatia, 2020; Kaur & Kumar, 2020; Manchanda et al., 2021). With 247 million users on YouTube and 159.75 million on Instagram, the United States came in second. Yet again, very few researches have been carried out here. However, due to the fast expansion of the cosmetic sector over the

past ten years in Indonesia, it is the most studied country, though it has a relatively smaller YouTube audience of 139 million people and an Instagram audience of 99.15 million users. An important proposition for future research is the increase of the geographic coverage to evaluate the efficacy of this marketing technique in both developed and emerging nations, given the rapid global rise of beauty vlogger marketing. Another understudied topic is the comparison of influencer effectiveness across nations, more specifically between developed and emerging nations. Cross-cultural research could indicate potential disparities in the relationships between influencers and followers based on cultural differences between nations, as well as international variations in consumer behaviour and influencer marketing communication.

6.2.3 Social media platform focus

A majority of the studies used for this systematic review have taken YouTube and Instagram as their primary content creation platform. Therefore, further studies are required to analyse individually other well-known social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter taking into account their content specialization. Additionally, the millennial generation and Generation Z are getting more and more interested in Snapchat and TikTok, two major content-creating platforms. Still, very few scholars have used these platforms in their research to evaluate how well marketing's influence on consumer behaviour is influenced by beauty. Future researchers are urged to incorporate these two platforms into their work in order to fully grasp the concept of beauty vlogger marketing. There are surprisingly few research that used various social media platforms. Future researchers can use a variety of platforms in their research because using different platform comparisons could also be extremely rewarding, especially since they afford the opportunity of exploring varied experiences because of distinctive audiences and different types of influencer attributes. Such research could very well assist in revealing whether generalizations regarding marketing by beauty vloggers across various social media platforms hold true and, if not, how they vary. Do they need to provide unique material for each social media platform? Can they post the same information across various platforms? What traits do beauty vloggers across social media platforms have in common? Do beauty vloggers have to provide product reviews for different brands on several social media sites? Do customers watch the same beauty vlogger on many platforms? How can beauty vloggers on various social media platforms disclose their sponsorships or collaborations with brands? Future study on these topics should attempt to clarify the similarities and differences between social media platforms in order to develop strategic business models that use social media as a most effective marketing tool.

6.3 Methodology

When compared to qualitative investigations, quantitative studies cover the majority of the ground, as was already indicated. As a new and developing phenomenon, we

advise upcoming researchers to carry out additional qualitative study to gain a thorough understanding of the marketing notion of beauty vloggers. Additionally, there are very few studies that use a mixed methods approach, yet scholars are urged to do so in order to address the need for more comprehensive insights. First, in keeping with this, practically all quantitative research has relied on a single source using Amazon Mechanical Turk (MTurk) for data collection, which is known as single-source bias. Therefore, it is advised that future researchers choose multiple sources while gathering the data in order to overcome this bias.

Second, non-probability sampling techniques like convenience and purposive sampling, which frequently cause biases in the selection of respondents and prevent the findings from being generalized, have been used frequently in various studies. Therefore, it is advised that future studies adopt random sampling techniques in order to address the drawbacks of non-probability sampling. Third, as opposed to longitudinal time horizon, cross-sectional time horizon has been utilised in the majority of researches. However, scholars may follow consumer behaviour in response to vlogger marketing at various points in time and track the various stages that the connection between audiences and beauty vloggers goes through over time, so longitudinal studies are crucial. Future researchers can thus incorporate longitudinal studies for improved understanding. Fourth, in order to assess actual customer interactions with the influencer objectively rather than dealing with consumers' retrospective views, researchers will need more interactive stimuli. The scholars may apply more real-life events by using case studies of beauty vloggers from various locations as well as case studies of different cosmetic brands using the vlogger marketing concept. This will lead to more valid results.

6.4 Limitations

This study has limitations, much like many other systematic and empirical studies. Although we made an effort to minimize the study's limitations, we were unable to completely overcome them. First, we only took into account English-language publications and thus ignored studies available in other languages that were published in peer-reviewed journals. We have taken into consideration a few conference proceedings as well because the material that is readily available on our issue is rather limited. However, none of the other types of grey literature, such as dissertations and book chapters, were included. Second, only three databases; Web of Science, Scopus, and EBSCOhost, were taken into account when choosing where to extract data from. Even though these three databases are well-known, it is possible that studies pertinent to our issue are also available in other databases. Third, it's possible that not all potentially pertinent studies were found using the search terms and filtering methods that were utilized. However, we are sure that the diligent reference checks and overall careful process of our systematic review have given us a representative sample of papers and decreased the likelihood that missed articles would have significantly changed our perspective and

conclusions.

7. Implications

7.1 Theoretical Implications

There is an abundance of available studies in the field of marketing and consumer behaviour. With changing time, the marketing techniques used by marketers are also changing, and hence the studies also move in the same direction. Though a plethora of studies exist in the existing body of knowledge related to social media marketing, influencer marketing, digital marketing, but very few systematic review studies are available especially considering beauty vloggers. This systematic review has interdisciplinary potential and can thus help future scholars to look for different outlooks in sub-areas using this study as their base.

Second, in this systematic review paper, variables used by different authors have been clubbed at one place which gives a broader view about the concept of beauty vloggers' influence. This review inculcates studies related to both qualitative and quantitative research area and hence provides a comprehensive research framework.

Third, the themes derived by synthesizing the existing literature can be used as groundwork for conducting in-depth qualitative study for building a deeper theoretical background in this rapidly upcoming sub-field of marketing. Not only qualitative analysis, but empirical studies can also be conducted using the variables derived from these themes using respondents from different geographical regions.

Fourth, this systematic review illuminates numerous future research avenues which can be used by prospective research scholars to develop new concepts regarding consumer behaviour. Moreover, Generation Z and baby boomers are techno-savvy generations. They use more social media than any other traditional sources of marketing. Therefore, understanding the use of social media platforms like YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, etc. as marketing tools and the role of beauty vloggers on these platforms will encourage researchers to get detailed knowledge about this phenomenon, hence augmenting marketing literature as a whole.

7.2 Practical Implications

In addition to the theoretical implications, this systematic review also provides various practical implications. By exploring the available literature, marketers can garner profound insights and knowledge about their existing customers, as also prospective ones. This study should help marketers to comprehend the complex emerging mechanisms of beauty vlogger influencing for maximizing their profit margins.

Second, considerable evidence scrutinized through this review makes it amply clear that influencer marketing is increasingly being visualized as more effective than celebrity endorsement as customers feel more familiarity,

and sense a higher level of credibility and authenticity with respect to beauty vloggers and the potentially dynamic interactions experienced with them. This is in stark contrast to the traditional, more static attraction of the celebrity. Moreover, choosing an appropriate beauty vlogger is a crucial marketing task, so marketers can consider user-influencer personality congruence or brand-influencer personality congruence before investing. The marketers of cosmetic brands with ambitions of a global presence may be justified in investing in different beauty vloggers for different regions where cultural backgrounds differ.

Now-a-days consumers are becoming more conscious about the ingredients as well as packaging of the product. Additionally, a section of consumers has started adopting a vegan lifestyle which encourages them to look for suitable vegan products. Unlike in case of celebrity endorsers, where advertising is in masses, such descriptions are generally informed about by beauty vloggers before promoting the products, thereby making their interactions more pertinent and inclusive. Flexibility and customisability are the cornerstones of such an approach. Thus, changing dynamics in the marketing domain make it important for marketers of cosmetic brands to explore and better understand the mechanism of beauty vlogger influencing.

Data Availability

The current study is a systematic literature review. All the research articles have been extracted from the three databases namely, web of Science, Scopus, and EBSCO host.

Declaration

The authors have no conflict of interest.

*Compliance with Ethical Standards

REFERENCES

1. Abdulla, A., & Saberi, M. (2026). The impact of social media influencers on customers' perceived brand equity in the Bahraini automobile industry. *Journal of Business and Socio-economic Development*, 6(1), 36-53.
2. Abdullah, T., Deraman, S. N., Zainuddin, S. A., Azmi, N. F., Abdullah, S. S., Anuar, N. I., . . . Hasan, H. (2020). Impact Of Social Media Influencer On Instagram User Purchase Intention Towards The Fashion Products: The Perspectives Of Students. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine* , 7(8), 2589-2598.
3. Afifah, N. (2019). The Influence of Beauty Vlogger's Content on the Purchase Intentions of Local Brands in Indonesia. *J. Mgt. Mkt. Review*, 4(4), 254-259.
4. Ananda, A. F., & Wandebori, H. (2016, September). The impact of drugstore makeup product reviews by beauty vlogger on YouTube towards purchase

- intention by undergraduate students in Indonesia. *International Conference on Ethics of Business, Economics, and Social Science*, 3(1), pp. 264-272.
5. Arendt, F., Till, B., Gutsch, A., & Niederkrotenthaler, T. (2025). Social media influencers and the Papageno effect: Experimental evidence for the suicide-preventive impact of social media posts on hope, healing, and recovery. *Social Science & Medicine*, 370, 117852.
 6. Balabanis, G., & Chatzopoulou, E. (2019). Under the influence of a blogger: The role of information-seeking goals and issue involvement. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(4), 342-353. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21182>
 7. Berryman, R., & Kavka, M. (2017). 'I Guess A Lot of People See Me as a Big Sister or a Friend': the role of intimacy in the celebrification of beauty vloggers. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 26(3), 307-320. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09589236.2017.1288611>
 8. Bhatia, A. (2020). Vlogging and the discursive co-construction of ethnicity and beauty. *World Englishes*, 39(1), 7-21. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/weng.12442>
 9. Borchers, N. S. (2025). How social media influencers support political parties in achieving campaign objectives, according to political communicators in Germany. *Public Relations Review*, 51, 102532.
 10. Britt, R. K., Hayes, J. L., Britt, B. C., & Park, H. (2020). Too Big to Sell? A computational analysis of network and content characteristics among mega and micro beauty and fashion social media influencers. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 20(2), 111-118. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2020.1763873>
 11. Carissa, Ayuaspharalinda, R., Tanuwidjaja, I. P., & Yuniarty. (2021). The Influence of Attitude Factors Toward Beauty Influencer on Brand Attitude and Consumers' Repurchase Intention. 2021 International Conference on Information Management and Technology (ICIMTech). 1, pp. 732-737. Jakarta, Indonesia: IEEE. doi:10.1109/ICIMTech53080.2021.9535041
 12. Castillo-Abdul, B., Romero-Rodríguez, L. M., & Balseca, J. (2021). Hola Followers! Content Analysis of YouTube Channels of Female Fashion Influencers in Spain and Ecuador. *Sage open*, 11(4). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211056609>
 13. Cheah, C. W., Koay, K. Y., & Lim, W. M. (2024). Social media influencer over-endorsement: Implications from a moderated-mediation analysis. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 79, 103831.
 14. Chen, J.-L., & Dermawan, A. (2020, April). The Influence of YouTube Beauty Vloggers on Indonesian Consumers' Purchase Intention of Local Cosmetic Products. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 15(5), 100-116. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v15n5p100>
 15. Choi, S. M., & Rifon, N. J. (2012). It Is a Match: The Impact of Congruence between Celebrity Image and Consumer Ideal Self on Endorsement Effectiveness. *Psychology of Marketing*, 29(9), 639-650. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.20550>
 16. Choi, W., & Lee, Y. (2019). Effects of fashion vlogger attributes on product attitude and content sharing. *Fashion and Textiles*, 6(1), 1-18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40691-018-0161-1>
 17. Costa, A. M., Troccoli, I. R., & altaf, J. g. (2021). Why Follow Beauty Blogs? An Investigation with Brazilian Consumers. *International journal of internet marketing and advertising*, 15(3), 281-301. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJIMA.2021.115423>
 18. Dekavalla, M. (2019). Gaining trust: the articulation of transparency by You Tube fashion and beauty content creators. *Media, Culture & Society*, 42(1), 75-92. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443719846613>
 19. Delbaere, M., Michael, B., & Phillips, B. J. (2020). Social media influencers: A route to brand engagement for their followers. *Psychology & Marketing*, 38(1), 101-112. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21419>
 20. Djafarova, E., & Matson, N. (2017). Credibility of digital influencers on YouTube and Instagram. *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*, 15(2), 131-148. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJIMA.2021.114338>
 21. Elseidi, R. I., & El-Baz, D. (2016, June). Electronic word of mouth effects on consumers' brand attitudes, brand image and purchase intention: an empirical study in Egypt. *The Business and Management Review*, 7(5), 268-276.
 22. Evers, J., & Daalmans, S. (2020). Influencer marketing 2.0. The success of beauty YouTubers' own brands. *TIJDSCHRIFT VOOR COMMUNICATIEWETENSCHAP*, 49(4), 298-321. doi:10.5117/TCW2021.4.002.EVER
 23. Fauzi, M. A., Ali, Z., Satari, Z., Ramli, P. A., & Omer, M. (2024). Social media in uencer marketing: science mapping of the present and future trends. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 16(2), 199-217.
 24. Feng, Y., Chen, H., & King, Q. (2020). An expert with whom i can identify: the role of narratives in influencer marketing. *International Journal of Advertising*, 40(7), 972-993. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2020.1824751>
 25. Freberg, K., Graham, K., McGaughey, K., & Freberg, L. A. (2011). Who are the social media influencers? A study of public perceptions of personality. *Public Relations Review*, 37(1), 90-92. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2010.11.001>
 26. García-Rapp, F. (2017). Popularity markers on YouTube's attention economy: the case of Bubzbeauty. *Celebrity studies*, 8(2), 228-245. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/19392397.2016.1242430>
 27. Garg, M., & Bakshi, A. (2024). Exploring the effects of audience and strategies used by beauty vloggers on behavioural intention towards endorsed brands.

- Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, 11(621), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03133-y>
28. Garg, M., & Bakshi, A. (2024). Exploring the impact of beauty vloggers' credible attributes, parasocial interaction, and trust on consumer purchase intention in influencer marketing. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(234), 1-14.
29. Gupta, H., Singh, S., & Sinha, P. (2017). Multimedia tool as a predictor for social media advertising-a YouTube way. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 76(18), 18557-18568. doi:10.1007/s11042-016-4249-6
30. Haenlein, M., Anadol, E., Farnsworth, T., Hugo, H., Hunichen, J., & Welte, D. (2020). Navigating the New Era of Influencer Marketing: How to be Successful on Instagram, TikTok, & Co. *California Management Review*, 63(1), 5-25. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125620958166>
31. Handriana, T., Dananjaya, D. I., Lestari, Y. D., & Aisyah, R. A. (2019). Parasocial Interaction between YouTube Beauty Vlogger and Millennial Consumers in Indonesia. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 9(8), 181-196.
32. Harst, J. P., & Angelopoulos, S. (2024). Less is more: Engagement with the content of social media influencers. *Journal of Business Research*, 181, 114746.
33. Hassan, S. H., Teo, S. Z., Ramaya, T., & Al-Kumaim, N. H. (2021). The credibility of social media beauty gurus in young millennials' cosmetic product choice. *Plos One*, 16(3), e0249286. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0249286>
34. Hermanda, A., Sumarwan, U., & Tinaprilla, N. (2019). The effect of social media influencer on brand image self concept, and purchase intention. *Journal of Consumer Sciences*, 4(2), 76-89. doi:<https://doi.org/10.29244/jcs.4.2.76-89>
35. Hou, M. (2018). Social media celebrity and the institutionalization of YouTube. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 25(3), 534-553. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856517750368>
36. Kaur, K., & Kumar, P. (2020). Social media usage in Indian beauty and wellness industry: A qualitative study. *The TQM Journal*, 33(1), 17-32. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-09-2019-0216>
37. Keasey, K., Lambrinouidakis, C., Mascia, D. V., & Zhang, Z. (2025). The impact of social media influencers on the financial market performance of firms. *European Financial Management*, 31(2), 745-785.
38. Ki, C.-W. '., & Kim, Y. K. (2019). The mechanism by which social media influencers persuade consumers: The role of consumers' desire to mimic. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(10), 905-922. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21244>
39. Kim, D. Y., & Kim, H.-Y. (2021). Trust me, trust me not: A nuanced view of influencer marketing on social media. *Journal of Business Research*, 134, 223-232. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.05.024>
40. Kim, J., & Kang, S. (2018). How social capital impacts the purchase intention of sustainable fashion products. *Journal of Business Research*, 117, 596-603. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.10.010>
41. Koay, K. Y., & Lim, W. M. (2025). Congruence effects in social media in uencer marketing: the moderating role of wishful identi cation in online impulse buying intentions. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 34(3), 265-278.
42. Konstantopoulou, A., Rizomyliotis, I., Konstantoulaki, K., & Badahdah, R. (2018). Improving SMEs' competitiveness with the use of Instagram influencer advertising and eWOM. *International journal of organizational analysis.*, 27(2), 308-321. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-04-2018-1406>
43. Kumar, A., Rayne, D., Salo, J., & Yiu, C. S. (2024). Battle of Influence: Analysing the Impact of Brand-Directed and Influencer-Directed Social Media Marketing on Customer Engagement and Purchase Behaviour. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 33(1), 87-95.
44. Ladhari, R., Massa, E., & Skandrani, H. (2020). YouTube vloggers' popularity and influence: The roles of homophily, emotional attachment, and expertise. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 54, 102027. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.102027>
45. Lee, J. E., & Watkins, B. (2016). YouTube vloggers' influence on consumer luxury brand perceptions and intentions. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(12), 5753-5760. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.04.171>
46. Lee, M., & Lee, H.-H. (2021). Do parasocial interactions and vicarious experiences in the beauty YouTube channels promote consumer purchase intention? *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 46(1), 235-248. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12667>
47. Lee, Y. W. (2019). Synergistics Co-operations in the Cosmetic Industry: Learning and Convergence between firms and social media. *Kritika Kultura*, 32, 237-259. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-02760-9>
48. Liu, H., Costa, M. F., Yasin, M. A.-I., & Ruan, Q. (2025). A study on how social media influences on impulsive buying. *Expert Systems*, 42(1), e13448.
49. Lopez, J., & Islam, S. (2021). Beauty Influencers and Instagram Usage. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 23(6), 184-200. doi:10.33423/jabe.v23i6.4686
50. Manchanda, P., Arora, N., & Sethi, V. (2021). Impact of Beauty Vlogger's Credibility and Popularity on eWOM Sharing Intention: The Mediating Role of Parasocial Interaction. *Journal of Promotion*

- Management, 28(3), 379-412. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10496491.2021.1989542>
51. Maulidy, A., Zaini, A. W., & Sanjani, M. A. (2025). Social Media Influence on Consumerism Trends Among College Students. *Indonesian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 4(1), 16-28.
52. Mccracken, G. (1989). Who Is the Celebrity Endorser? Cultural Foundations of the Endorsement Process. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 16(3), 310-321. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1086/209217>
53. Ndasi, W., & Cheung, M. L. (2026). Navigating influence: a mixed-method study on the role of social Management media influencer type and message content in driving digital engagement and patronage intentions. *International Journal of Hospitality*, 132, 104401.
54. Nosita, F., & Lestari, T. (2019). The Influence of User Generated Content and Purchase Intention on Beauty Products. *Journal of Management and Marketing Review*, 4(3), 171-183.
55. Nugraha, A. K., & Agus, A. A. (2020). Analysis of Homophily, Emotional Attachment, and Expertise towards Vloggers' Popularity and Viewers Purchasing Decisions in Beauty Products Industry. 2020 3rd International Conference on Computer and Informatics Engineering (IC2IE) (pp. 13-18). Yogyakarta, Indonesia: IEEE. doi:10.1109/IC2IE50715.2020.9274675
56. Paul, J., & Criado, A. R. (2020). The art of writing literature review: What do we know and what do we need to know? *International Business Review*, 29(4), 101717. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2020.101717>
57. Pei, Y., Wu, J., Wang, F., & Wang, S. (2026). Unwavering interests in influencers: Influencer-focused barrages in social media product review videos. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 88, 104485.
58. Putri, L. W., & Setiawan, B. L. (2025). ANALYZING THE STRATEGIC CONTRIBUTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCERS TO E-COMMERCE MARKETING EFFECTIVENESS. *JUMDER: Jurnal Bisnis Digital Dan Ekonomi Kreatif*, 1(2).
59. Putri, T. U., & Abdinagoro, S. B. (2018). Response to a New Wave in Digital Marketing: Does Beauty Blogger Involvement The Most Influencing Factor in Halal Cosmetic Purchase Intention. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 7(6), 446-452.
60. Ramadanty, S., Muqarrabin, A. M., Nita, W. A., & Syafganti, I. (2020). Examining the Effect of Persuasive Message of Beauty Vloggers on Information Acceptance of eWOM and Purchase Intention: The Study of Consumers of Beauty Products in Jabodetabek, Indonesia. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 28(2), 763-775.
61. Rosara, N. A., & Luthfia, A. (2020). Factors Influencing Consumer's Purchase Intention on Beauty Products in YouTube. *Journal of Distribution Science*, 18(6), 37-46. doi:<https://doi.org/10.15722/jds.18.6.202006.37>
62. Sánchez-Fernández, R., & Jiménez-Castillo, D. (2021, January). How social media influencers affect behavioural intentions towards recommended brands: the role of emotional attachment and information value. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 37(11-12), 1-25. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2020.1866648>
63. Sanny, L., Arina, A. N., Maulidya, R. T., & Pertiwi, R. P. (2020). Purchase intention on Indonesia male's skin care by social media marketing effect towards brand image and brand trust. *Management Science Letters*, 10(10), 2139-2146. doi:10.5267/j.msl.2020.3.023
64. Schimmelpfennig, C. (2018). Who is the Celebrity Endorser? A Content Analysis of Celebrity Endorsements. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 30(4), 220-234. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08961530.2018.1446679>
65. Schouten, A. P., Janssen, L., & Verspaget, M. (2019). Celebrity vs. Influencer endorsements in advertising: the role of identification, credibility, and Product-Endorser fit. *International Journal of Advertising*, 39(2), 1-24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2019.1634898>
66. Simanjuntak, M., Nguyen, M., & Situmeang, F. (2017). To What Extent Do Beauty Bloggers Influence the Purchase Behavior of Their Audience? Exploring the Links Between Consumer Personality and Blog Preferences. *Advanced Science Letters*, 23(1), 623-627. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2017.7278>
67. Sokolova, K., & Kefi, H. (2020). Instagram and YouTube bloggers promote it, why should I buy? How credibility and parasocial interaction influence purchase intentions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 53. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.01.011>
68. Spori-Wang, K., Krause, F., & Henkel, S. (2025). Predictors of social media influencer marketing effectiveness: A comprehensive literature review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 186, 114991.
69. Sutanto, M. A., & Aprianingsih, A. (2016). The effect of online consumer review toward purchase intention: A study in premium cosmetic in Indonesia. *International Conference on Ethics of Business, Economics, and Social Science*, (pp. 218-230).
70. Tafheem, N., El-Gohary, H., & Sobh, R. (2022). Social Media User-Influencer Congruity: An Analysis of Social Media Platforms Parasocial Relationships. *International Journal of Customer Relationship Marketing and Management*, 13(1), 1-26. doi:10.4018/IJCRMM.289213
71. Torres, P., Augusto, M., & Matos, M. (2019). Antecedents and outcomes of digital influencer endorsement: An exploratory study. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(12), 1267-1276. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21274>

72. Tran, V. D., & Nguyena, H. A. (2020). Consumer attitudes towards beauty bloggers and paid blog advertisements on purchase intention in Veitnam. *Management Science Letters*, 10(5), 1017-1026. doi:10.5267/j.msl.2019.11.008
73. Wang, S.-J., Hsu, C.-P., Huang, H.-C., & Chen, C.-L. (2015). How readers' perceived self-congruity and functional congruity affect bloggers' informational influence Perceived interactivity as a moderator. *Online Information Review*, 39(4), 537-555. doi:https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-02-2015-0063
74. Wiedmann, K.-P., & Mettenheim, W. V. (2020). Attractiveness, trustworthiness and expertise – social influencers' winning formula? *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 30(5), 707-725. doi: https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBM-06-2019-2442
75. Zhang, H. (2018). Vlogger's engagement via facebook: A case study of UK beauty Vlogger Zoella. In V. Cunnane, & N. Corcoron (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 5th European Conference on Social Media, ECSM 2018* (pp. 479-484). Ireland: Curran Associates proceedings. Retrieved from https://shura.shu.ac.uk/id/eprint/25277.
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